

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable

Deliverable: D7.5 Operation Activities Report (interim)

30/04/2021

NEANIAS is funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme via grant agreement No. 863448

D7.5 Operation Activities Report (interim)

Document Info

Project Information			
Acronym	NEANIAS		
Name	Novel EOSC Services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater & Space Challenges		
Start Date	1 Nov 2019	End Date	31 Oct 2022
Program	H2020-EU.1.4.1.3. - Development, deployment and operation of ICT-based e-infrastructures		
Call ID	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-2020	Topic	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2019-1
Grant No	863448	Instrument	RIA
Document Information			
Deliverable No	D7.5		
Deliverable Title	Operation Activities Report (interim)		
Due Date	30-APR-2021	Delivery Date	10-MAY-2021
Lead Beneficiary	GARR		
Beneficiaries (part.)	NKUA, INAF, SZTAKI, CORONIS, CITE, UOP, TELEDYNE, UNIMIB, JACOBSUNI, MEEO, GARR, ALTEC		
Editor(s)	Claudio Pisa (GARR)		
Authors (s)	Nikos Chondros (NKUA), Michalis Konstantopoulos (NKUA), Claudio Pisa (GARR), Konstantinos Kakaletis (CITE), Giorgos Papanikos (CITE), Attila Farkas (SZTAKI), Laura Vettorello (MEEO), Gergely Sipos (SZTAKI)		
Contributor (s)	Alex Barchiesi (GARR), Efstratios Giannopoulos (CITE)		
Reviewer(s)	Christos Evangelidis (NOA)		
Workpackage No	WP7 – Delivery		
Version	v1	Stage	Final
Version details	Revision: 42 . Last save: 2021-05-10 , 07:45 Pages: 33 . Characters: 33.199		
Distribution	Public	Type	Report
Keywords	Delivery, EOSC, Quality metrics, operation, monitoring		

Change Record

version	Date	Change Description	Editor	Change Location (page/section)
1	10/05/2021	Document Version submitted to EC	Claudio Pisa	

Disclaimer

NEANIAS is a Research and Innovation Action funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, via grant agreement No. 863448.

NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the 'Prototyping New Innovative Services' challenge set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community's research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighboring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

This document has been produced receiving funding from the European Commission. The content of this document is a product of the NEANIAS project Consortium and it does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The editor, author, contributors and reviewers of this document have taken any available measure in order for its content to be accurate and lawful. However, neither the project consortium as a whole nor the individual partners

that implicitly or explicitly participated in the creation and publication of this document may be held responsible for any damage, financial or other loss or any other issue that may arise as a result of using the content of this document or any of the project outputs that this document may refer to.

The European Union (EU) was established in accordance with the Treaty on the European Union (Maastricht). There are currently 28 member states of the European Union. It is based on the European Communities and the member states' cooperation in the fields of Common Foreign and Security Policy and Justice and Home Affairs. The five main institutions of the European Union are the European Parliament, the Council of Ministers, the European Commission, the Court of Justice, and the Court of Auditors (<http://europa.eu.int/>).

Table of Contents

Document Info	2
Change Record	3
Disclaimer	4
Table of Contents	5
Tables of Figures & Tables	6
Abstract	7
1. Introduction	8
1.1. Context	8
1.2. Contents and Rationale	8
1.3. Structure of the Document	8
2. Operation Activities	9
2.1. Service Deployment	9
2.1.1. <i>Development, Staging and Production environments</i>	9
2.1.2. <i>Service deployment models</i>	9
2.2. Operational services support activities	12
2.2.1. <i>Service Management System</i>	12
2.2.2. <i>GARR Cloud</i>	13
2.2.3. <i>NEANIAS Gitlab</i>	14
2.2.4. <i>Read The Docs</i>	14
2.2.5. <i>DNS Operations</i>	15
2.2.6. <i>PKI Operations</i>	15
2.2.7. <i>Backups</i>	16
2.3. Monitoring and alerting	17
2.3.1. <i>NEANIAS monitoring and alerting</i>	17
2.3.2. <i>EOSC integrated monitoring (ARGO)</i>	19
2.3.3. <i>GARR Cloud resource usage monitoring</i>	19
3. Operational Performance	20
3.1. Operations at a glance	22
3.1.1. <i>EOSC Integrated monitoring (ARGO)</i>	22
3.1.2. <i>NEANIAS monitoring and alerting</i>	23
3.1.3. <i>NEANIAS Accounting and logging core services</i>	26
3.1.4. <i>Service Management System</i>	29
4. Conclusions	31
References	32
List of acronyms	33

Tables of Figures & Tables

Document Figures

Figure 2.1 - S1 service, OpenNebula template	11
Figure 2.2 - S1 service, OpenNebula template (disk)	12
Figure 2.3 - NEANIAS Gitlab dashboard screenshot	14
Figure 2.4 - NEANIAS monitoring architecture diagram	17
Figure 2.5 - Juju deployment diagram	18
Figure 3.1 - ARGO dashboard for NEANIAS core services	22
Figure 3.2 – ARGO: Monthly availability & reliability table for NEANIAS AAI	22
Figure 3.3 – ARGO: Monthly availability & reliability charts for NEANIAS AAI	23
Figure 3.4 - NEANIAS monitoring Grafana dashboard	23
Figure 3.5 - NEANIAS monitoring Grafana dashboard	24
Figure 3.6 - NEANIAS monitoring Grafana dashboard	24
Figure 3.7 – Nagios: Service Status	25
Figure 3.8 – Nagios: Service availability report	25
Figure 3.9 – NEANIAS AAI accountable actions tracked using NEANIAS Accounting Service	26
Figure 3.10 - Log aggregation and statistics using NEANIAS Logging Service	27
Figure 3.11 - Log filtering using NEANIAS Logging Service	28
Figure 3.12 NEANIAS SMS Redmine project	29
Figure 3.13 NEANIAS SMS documentation as Redmine Wiki	29
Figure 3.14 NEANIAS SMS User ticket creation	30

Document Tables

Table 1 Identified metric vs monitoring tool matrix	21
---	----

Abstract

This document, deliverable D7.5 “Operation Activities Report (interim)”, reports on the operation activities of the project and their performance regarding targets set. It addresses the activities concerning NEANIAS thematic and core service deployment, monitoring and support. Moreover, this document reports on the metrics and tools aimed at assessing service performance.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

WP7 “Services Delivery and Operation” supports the NEANIAS Service delivery and operation by interacting with i) WP8 for the EOSC integration, ii) the thematic work packages WP2, WP3 and WP4 as adapted to the business cases through WP5, and iii) the core services established by WP6.

1.2. Contents and Rationale

One of the objectives of WP7 is to provide in operation the NEANIAS services, to their corresponding end-users on resources capable to deliver the required quality of service. This document, deliverable D7.5, “Operation Activities Report (interim)”, addresses the operation activities of the project and their performance regarding targets set, which stem from the work performed mainly in task T7.3 “Operational services provisioning”. The underlying integrated infrastructures are described in deliverable D7.4, while the tools employed for the delivery tasks are described in deliverables D7.1 [1] and D7.3 [2].

1.3. Structure of the Document

The document is partitioned in two main sections. Section 2, “Operation Activities” reports on the performed and ongoing activities concerning service deployment environments, service deployment models and service operation and monitoring. Section 3 “Operational Performance” focuses instead on the collection and analysis of service metrics.

2. Operation Activities

2.1. Service Deployment

2.1.1. Development, Staging and Production environments

In the NEANIAS AAI service, we have segregated three different realms, and we provide for three corresponding deployment environments:

- **Development (DNS subdomain “dev”):** This is an integration environment where partners deploy the latest version of their services, after they have passed their internal testing, to provide visibility to “outsiders”, i.e., people outside the core development team. This is also an “integration testing” release environment, as API providing services are first deployed here to be tested by external actors (service consumers). Due to scarcity of resources, we have agreed that each partner will host services running under the development environment on his/her own infrastructure but will make such services available 24/7 so that other partners or external actors (such as business domain users) can test their own software against newer releases of services.
- **Staging (DNS subdomain “staging”):** For services running under Kubernetes, we have deployed a separate Kubernetes cluster in the GARR Cloud with fewer nodes than the production one but identical configuration. This provides the opportunity to service providers to deploy their services in the staging environment first, and test that everything is working as expected. This is especially important because of our decision to disallow services in the “development” realm to deploy at GARR. For services running as VMs we do not offer such an environment, due to lack of resources.
- **Production (no DNS subdomain):** This is the production deployment environment for all services. For the ones running under Kubernetes, a cluster is available on top of OpenStack that is closely monitored by the GARR team for meeting its availability guarantees. For services that deploy using VMs, each service provider manages their own set of VMs that comprise their corresponding service. Finally, a bare-metal based Kubernetes cluster is also available, mostly for Machine Learning deployments, but we discourage its use and propose the use of the OpenStack based one.

2.1.2. Service deployment models

2.1.2.1. Virtual Machine deployment

Deliverable D7.4 “Infrastructures integration report (interim)” [3] reports on the infrastructures employed by NEANIAS services. NEANIAS service providers can employ IaaS platforms based on OpenStack and OpenNebula to create virtual machines, leveraging compute and storage resources.

This approach may leverage platform-specific cloud facilities, such as platform-specific load balancers and firewalls, the drawback being the decreased portability of the service to different cloud infrastructures.

D7.5 Operation Activities Report (interim)

2.1.2.2. Kubernetes Deployment

For services that deploy using Kubernetes, continuous integration can be achieved using Gitlab's functionality. NEANIAS has its own Gitlab instance (deployed under gitlab.neanias.eu). The main component of the process is a Gitlab runner, which executes unit and integration tests, builds Docker images, and, finally, deploys the service on the target environment.

NEANIAS Gitlab provides a "shared" runner, which any service can use to perform operations such as building docker images and executing tests. However, to allow a runner to deploy the service in a specific environment, e.g., the "dev" subdomain, each partner deploys a private runner, in the same Kubernetes cluster and namespace that the service is deployed, so that the runner has access to the cluster's resources, under the service provider's access rights.

Using the above tools and conventions, one of the policies that can be adopted by service providers that are deploying to the production Kubernetes cluster is the following:

1. Use the provided "shared" runner for any step of the process that does not require access to the resources of a specific deployment environment.
2. Create a Gitlab runner in each Kubernetes cluster that the service provider is using. These runners are tagged under Gitlab with the name of the corresponding environment (development, staging and production).
3. Use feature branches to develop new features, create bug fixes and document the changes in a changelog.
4. Use merge requests to integrate changes of these features to the master branch.
5. Create a Gitlab pipeline action to execute tests of the service upon creating a merge request to master branch, and accept the merge request only when all tests succeed.
6. Release the service to the development environment:
 - a. Create a new Gitlab release with semantic versioning.
 - b. Setup the shared runner to build a new docker image, tag it with the version number of the release, and push it to the container registry of the service.
 - c. Setup the development runner to deploy the new release to the development environment.
 - d. Setup the shared runner to execute integration tests with the remaining NEANIAS services on the development environment.
7. Potentially create a new round of User Acceptance testing from a broader audience than the core development team.
8. Use merge requests to the production branch, to integrate new releases to staging and production environments.
9. Release the service to the staging environment:
 - a. Setup the staging runner to deploy the new release to the staging environment when merging from master to production branch.
 - b. Potentially setup the shared runner to execute integration tests on the staging environment.
 - c. Verify integration with components that are identical to the production environment.
10. Release the service to the production environment:
 - a. Setup production runner to deploy the new release to the production environment, after manual verification of the staging environment.

D7.5 Operation Activities Report (interim)

2.1.2.3. OpenNebula deployment

In the NEANIAS project, the MEEO Cloud offers the virtual resources in an OpenNebula instance. The deployment process goes through some preliminary steps such as the definition of a template. Figure 2.1 and Figure 2.2 show an example for the S1 services, in the context of Work Package 4.

The screenshot displays the 'Update VM Template' configuration page for the 'explorer-space-dev' template. The interface includes a navigation bar with tabs for 'General', 'Storage', 'Network', 'OS Booting', 'Input/Output', 'Actions', 'Context', 'Scheduling', and 'Hybrid'. The 'General' tab is active, showing the following fields:

- Name:** explorer-space-dev
- Description:** (empty text area)
- Memory:** 8 GB (with a cost of 0.00 per month)
- CPU:** 2 (with a cost of 0.00 per month)
- VCPU:** 2 (with a cost of 0.00 per month)
- Hypervisor:** Radio buttons for KVM (selected) and vCenter
- Logo:** (empty dropdown menu)
- Memory modification:** any value (dropdown)
- CPU modification:** any value (dropdown)
- VCPU modification:** any value (dropdown)

Figure 2.1 - S1 service, OpenNebula template

The template's requirements should be defined in collaboration with the service provider. This process has to define:

- required memory and CPU;
- one or more virtual networks and their policies;
- a set of disks with persistent images;
- optional attributes that could be useful for the deployment.

D7.5 Operation Activities Report (interim)

Figure 2.2 - S1 service, OpenNebula template (disk)

The templates are persistent, it means they are stored in the system for future reuse.

The network interfaces are defined like other resources needed by the VM. This type of automatic selection can recognise the required network type and it will be automatically selected among those available in the cluster.

After the template definition, the deployment goes ahead with the effective resources allocation and the needed configuration. After that, the service provider will be able to connect to the OpenNebula resource and to deploy the service by its own procedure.

At the current status, there aren't any services deployed via Docker in the MEEO OpenNebula instance. However, it has a dedicated client to manage Docker containers and also native features for this objective, therefore this kind of deployment could be potentially supported.

2.1.2.4. Linux containers

Linux containers are a type of lightweight operating system level virtualization, in which different containers share the same operating system kernel.

In particular, Docker containers [4] offer a popular way to package and deliver applications, and are widely supported by different platforms.

While Docker containers are oriented towards application packaging to implement microservices applications, and tend to minimize the image sizes to include only the strictly needed dependencies, LXC containers [5] address the need for full operating system virtualization, where several applications are running on the same system.

Please note that for what concerns NEANIAS services, Linux containers are deployed in virtual machines or Kubernetes clusters (where they are named *Pods*).

2.2. Operational services support activities

2.2.1. Service Management System

The NEANIAS Service Management System (SMS) is based on the Redmine ticketing system. The Redmine instance and the backend database are deployed as Docker containers. The NEANIAS SMS supports the NEANIAS AAI for authentication and minimal authorization for admin access. There are two different versions of the SMS system, development and staging version with different databases in the current status. The development version can be deployed via a docker compose for local development purposes. The staging version is

D7.5 Operation Activities Report (interim)

deployed in the staging Kubernetes cluster with reverse proxy and HTTPS functionality and integrated with NEANIAS AAI in the staging realm. The staging database is deployed on the GARR Cloud platform as a docker container with manual backups. The production version of the SMS will be deployed in the production Kubernetes cluster with HTTPS and production AAI integration. The production SMS database will be deployed in the central NEANIAS database.

Currently, the procedures which are described in Deliverable D8.2 [6] are implemented in the SMS system. The FitSM procedures are realized with custom issue types and custom workflows. The SMS system supports Access request for the different thematic services. To provide the Helpdesk functionality, the users can submit Complaints, Incidents, Change requests and Improvement requests for the services. Currently, the SMS provides a generic request workflow for the internal processes, but it will support more specific processes like Service Portfolio Management (SPM), Service Level Management (SLM) and Release and deployment management (RDM). The whole NEANIAS SMS system is documented as Redmine Wiki pages.

2.2.2. GARR Cloud

Most of the NEANIAS services rely on the GARR Cloud as their underlying infrastructure. To ensure access to the GARR Cloud IaaS and PaaS resources the GARR Cloud administrators perform the following tasks:

- Partition the compute and storage resources in different OpenStack projects and Kubernetes namespaces, setting the appropriate quotas for storage and computing resources
- Accept NEANIAS user registrations to the GARR Cloud and assign them to the appropriate OpenStack projects and namespaces. The registration (and login) can be performed through three supported authentication methods:
 1. IDEM/eduGAIN (SAML)
 2. Google (OIDC)
 3. Form registration
- Notify the users that they can access the GARR Cloud facilities and provide them with instructions and documentation

The GARR Cloud support can be contacted via e-mail at the address cloud-support@garr.it, which automatically creates tickets in the GARR ticketing system.

Concerning the security procedures of the GARR Cloud team, these are certified ISO/IEC 27001.

D7.5 Operation Activities Report (interim)

2.2.3. NEANIAS Gitlab

The NEANIAS Gitlab supports service development and deployment through CI/CD facilities. The NEANIAS Gitlab supports the NEANIAS AAI for authentication. When a user performs the access to the NEANIAS Gitlab through the NEANIAS AAI, a new Gitlab user is created. By default, this newly created user will be in the “blocked” status, and will not be able to perform any tasks. The Gitlab administrator performs the task of unblocking these users and assigning them to groups and Gitlab projects.

Figure 2.3 shows a screenshot of the NEANIAS Gitlab featuring statistics such as the number of users, projects and groups at the time of writing.

Figure 2.3 - NEANIAS Gitlab dashboard screenshot

2.2.4. Read The Docs

As reported in Deliverables D7.1 [1], D7.2 [8] and D7.4 [3], the NEANIAS services documentation is hosted by *Read the Docs* (<https://readthedocs.org>). When a service provider, who already has a documentation git repository in the NEANIAS Gitlab, expresses the need for documentation hosting the following steps are performed:

1. A new Read the Docs project is created as a subproject of the main NEANIAS project. The name of the new Read the Docs project is returned to the service provider
2. A webhook is created in Read the Docs, linked to the Git repository hosting the service documentation. The Webhook URL is returned to the service provider
3. The service provider adds the webhook URL returned from step 2 to the webhooks of the Gitlab project hosting the service documentation Git repository. This webhook should be triggered when a new commit is pushed to the repository
4. The service provider edits the root documentation Git repository to add a link to their service documentation, using the service identifier yielded in step 1.

Service providers are not required to have an account at Read the Docs, but they might wish to do so to configure advanced options (e.g. documentation localization options).

2.2.5. DNS Operations

The NEANIAS DNS contains DNS records of NEANIAS services that need to have a public fully qualified name (FQDN) or special DNS records (i.e. TXT records, MX records, etc).

DNS records are created on the first deployment of a service, after a request from the service provider to the NEANIAS DNS zone administrators (managed by CITE). Records can be altered, if needed, following the same procedure, in case the service needs to be accessible using another IP or proxy.

The following naming convention is followed (§ Section 2.1.1):

- For services running in the production environment, the main domain name is used for creating the related DNS records, i.e. <service>.neanias.eu
- For services running in the staging environment a subdomain named staging.neanias.eu is used (i.e. <service>.staging.neanias.eu.
- For services running in the development environment a subdomain named staging.neanias.eu is used (i.e. <service>.dev.neanias.eu.

If the service is accessed directly through a dedicated public IP then a type A DNS record is used. If the service is running behind a proxy then a DNS record of type CNAME is used, pointing to the related proxy.

In the cases where a proxy or a service is served by many nodes, multiple DNS records may be created for the same service, using the corresponding IP address for each service node, to achieve DNS load balancing.

Currently there are more than 75 DNS records in the neanias.eu zone, which are managed by the DNS administrators through a user interface with restricted access. DNS names of interest to the public are listed in the NEANIAS Catalogue [7].

2.2.6. PKI Operations

NEANIAS public key infrastructure (PKI) is used for the creation, storage and revocation of digital certificates which are used to verify that a particular public key belongs to a certain NEANIAS service. It is used for creating certificates only for NEANIAS services. These certificates are used for encryption/authentication/authorization between NEANIAS services.

The NEANIAS PKI is deployed on CITE's infrastructure and the activities taking place by its administrators are:

- Creation of a certificate: the NEANIAS PKI is signing certificate signing requests that are sent to NEANIAS PKI administration by NEANIAS service providers.
- Storage of issued certificates: all issued certificates are stored in the PKI and can be sent again to the service provider at any point, if needed.
- Certificate renewal (same private key): At any point, a service provider may request for a renewal of a certificate. At this stage, the service provider may ask for a "subject" change too. The renewal of a certificate is not requiring a new certificate request.
- Re-issue a certificate: re-issuing is required when the service provider needs to change the private key of the service. For example, if the key is lost or compromised. In that case the previous certificates are being revoked and a new one is created.
- Certificate revocation: Is taking place when a service provider informs the NEANIAS PKI that a key is decommissioned or was stolen or was changed. In that case the certificates for this key are revoked.

D7.5 Operation Activities Report (interim)

- Revocation list creation: Each time a certificate is revoked a new Certificate Revocation List (CRL) is created and then is posted on ca.neanias.eu
 - http://ca.neanias.eu/crl/neanias_ca.crl
 - http://ca.neanias.eu/crl/neanias_root_ca.crl

2.2.7. Backups

All information available as “volumes” in OpenStack at GARR is backed by the Ceph filesystem, which guarantees triple redundancy. As such, we are certain that there are no single points of failure in the storage layer.

However, we have agreed and announced to all service providers that this does not constitute a proper backup policy, as it does not protect against human errors, or more severe multiple-machine failure situations.

To address this, we have alerted all service provider that each one should have his/her own backup policy, and also an implementation, that satisfied business continuity needs as required by their respective SLAs.

As an example policy, a service provider may backup all persistent state to their own Data Sharing service (Nextcloud) account at frequent intervals, and offload them from there to storage outside of GARR, always ensuring that security concerns are properly addressed.

To implement their backup policies, service providers can also leverage object store facilities, like the one provided by the Data Depositing Service core service (i.e. the GARR Cloud Platform Object Store). To this aim, some tools, such as Rclone (<https://rclone.org/>), support object storage client-side encryption.

For some infrastructural services, such as Gitlab and the monitoring systems, regular snapshots of the OpenStack volumes are performed. These snapshots add redundancy and can be used to recover the systems in case of accidental data loss.

2.3. Monitoring and alerting

2.3.1. NEANIAS monitoring and alerting

Monitoring is the key service needed to gain insights into an infrastructure. It needs to be continuous and on-demand to quickly detect, correlate, and analyse data for a fast reaction to anomalous behaviour. The challenge of this type of monitoring is how to quickly identify and correlate problems before they affect end-users and ultimately the productivity of their organizations. The features of a monitoring system are monitoring of services, reporting availability and reliability, visualization of the services status, providing dashboard interfaces and sending real-time alerts. Management teams, administrators, service owners can monitor the availability and reliability of the services from a high-level view down to individual system metrics and monitor the conformance of multiple SLAs.

The NEANIAS monitoring infrastructure has been deployed through the Juju automation tool in the GARR Cloud. It is composed by the following components:

- Nagios - a monitoring and alerting system
- NRPE (Nagios Remote plugin executor) - an agent to execute Nagios probes on remote systems
- InfluxDB - a time series database
- Nagflux – a metrics collector from Nagios to InfluxDB
- Grafana - a platform for data visualization, querying and alerting
- Prometheus - a monitoring and alerting tool
- Telegraf – an agent for collecting, processing, aggregating and writing metrics

Figure 2.4 - NEANIAS monitoring architecture diagram

Figure 2.4 depicts the devised monitoring and alerting architecture. The NEANIAS services deployed on virtual machines on top of *OpenStack* or *OpenNebula* are monitored through *Nagios*. *Nagflux* inserts the metrics collected by the Nagios probes in an *InfluxDB* database. NEANIAS services deployed on *Kubernetes* clusters are instead monitored through *telegraf*,

D7.5 Operation Activities Report (interim)

which is responsible for sending the collected metrics to *Prometheus*. *Grafana* can then perform data visualization for data stored both in Prometheus and InfluxDB.

The infrastructure described above has been implemented as a microservices architecture composed by virtual machines and LXC containers, through the *Juju* automation system.

Figure 2.5 shows the deployed microservices (or *charms* using Juju terminology) and their relations.

Figure 2.5 - Juju deployment diagram

Service providers, to monitor their virtual machine based services, should deploy a Nagios probe (NRPE). An Ansible playbook has been provided in the NEANIAS Gitlab to automate this step. Then, to update the Nagios configuration to take into account the new service, the service provider should produce a new commit in the nagios-configuration Git repository on the NEANIAS Gitlab, specifying the IP address of the NRPE probe. These commits trigger a CI/CD pipeline which checks for the correctness of the commit. If this check passes, the actual Nagios configuration is updated with the new service.

The default NRPE and Nagios configurations perform only general checks, so that these can be applied to all services. However, service providers are encouraged to provide their service specific probes. For example, checks for the existence of specific strings in a web page, certificate status, fail2ban status, user login, antivirus reporting, etc.

To monitor Kubernetes based services through Prometheus, service providers can either expose an HTTP endpoint on their application providing Prometheus formatted metrics, deploy a *telegraf* “sidecar” in their service pods or use the telegraf Kubernetes operator. Also the NEANIAS kubernetes clusters resources themselves are monitored through Prometheus.

2.3.2. EOSC integrated monitoring (ARGO)

The EGI e-infrastructure federation provides service monitoring service in EOSC (<http://argoeu.github.io/index.html>) based on the ARGO system. This ARGO-based Service collects service status results from monitoring engine(es) and delivers status results and/or monthly availability (A) and reliability (R) statistics of distributed services. Both the status results and A/R statistics are presented through a Web UI, with the possibility for users to drill-down from the availability of a site to individual services, to individual test results that contributed to overall reliability/availability of the service. Argo is capable also to send notifications to the service admins in case of a failure/warning on one of the services monitored.

ARGO Service Monitoring keeps an eye on the performance of IT services and quickly detects issues and helps the providers resolve them. With Service Monitoring service providers can get:

- the activation of monitoring for their services with minimal effort
- a ready-to-use user interface
- automated reporting tools

The NEANIAS project engaged with the EGI ARGO team and two of the NEANIAS services (AAI and DaShaS) have been configured into the EGI Monitor [10]. Based on this initial positive experience the project is now moving forward and getting NEANIAS thematic services monitored too, as part of their onboarding into the EOSC Portal.

2.3.3. GARR Cloud resource usage monitoring

The usage of the GARR Cloud resources employed by the NEANIAS project is periodically reviewed. This allows to accommodate the services requirements as the need arises.

For security reasons, as the operation requires administrative rights on the GARR Cloud, the resource usage collection is performed through an automated script leveraging the OpenStack command line client, but triggered manually by the GARR staff.

3. Operational Performance

The operational performance of the NEANIAS thematic and core services is assessed against the quality metrics which are relevant for operational performance, among the set of recommended quality metrics included in Deliverable D7.1 [1]. In particular we consider the following metrics:

- Metrics related to service operation:
 - Returning users
 - Number of (HTTP) requests
 - Latency of HTTP requests
 - Network reachability
 - Network latency
 - Number of errors
 - Number of pending security updates
 - Incidents
- Service metrics to be reported towards EOSC (through the available EOSC interfaces and facilities) and used by the SLM, SACM and ISRM FitSM processes:
 - Service requests
 - Service users
 - Service usage
 - Service capacity
 - Service availability
 - Service reliability
 - Service serviceability/durability
- Metrics related to user support, to be used by the CRM, RDM and ISRM FitSM processes:
 - Turnaround time for issues initiated by external users
 - Turnaround time for issues initiated by NEANIAS internal users

These metrics are assessed through the monitoring tools described in deliverable D7.1 [1], D7.2 [8], D7.3 [2] and D7.4 [3] and relevant services among the NEANIAS core services described in deliverable D6.1 [9]:

- EGI ARGO - EOSC integrated monitoring (§ deliverable D7.1 [1], Section 0 of this document)
- Nagios based monitoring (§ deliverable D7.1 [1], deliverable D7.2 [8], Section 3.1.2 of his document)
- Accounting service (§ deliverable D6.1 [9])
- Logging service (§ deliverable D6.1 [9])
- SMS system (§ deliverable D7.3 [2], deliverable D7.4 [3])

D7.5 Operation Activities Report (interim)

Table 1 summarizes how the identified metrics are matched by the deployed monitoring tools and by the Accounting and Logging core services.

Metric / Monitoring tool	KPI Target	ARGO	Nagios	Accounting Service	Logging Service	SMS System
Metrics related to service operation						
Returning Users	25%			X		
Number of (HTTP) requests			X		X	
Latency of HTTP requests		X	X			
Network Reachability		X	X			
Network Latency		X	X			
Number of errors			X		X	
Number of pending security updates			X		X	
Incidents						X
Service metrics to be reported towards EOSC and FitSM						
Service requests			X		X	
Service Users				X		X
Service usage			X	X	X	X
Service capacity				X		X
Service availability	99.9%	X	X			
Service reliability		X	X			X
Service serviceability/durability						X
Metrics related to user support						
Turnaround time for critical issues initiated by external users	2 days average					X
Turnaround time for issues initiated by NEANIAS internal users						X

Table 1 Identified metric vs monitoring tool matrix

D7.5 Operation Activities Report (interim)

3.1. Operations at a glance

3.1.1. EOSC Integrated monitoring (ARGO)

The screenshots in Figure 3.1, Figure 3.2 and Figure 3.3 show the NEANIAS specific dashboard of the EGI ARGO monitoring system, publicly accessible at [10].

Figure 3.1 - ARGO dashboard for NEANIAS core services

Figure 3.2 – ARGO: Monthly availability & reliability table for NEANIAS AAI

D7.5 Operation Activities Report (interim)

Figure 3.3 – ARGO: Monthly availability & reliability charts for NEANIAS AAI

3.1.2. NEANIAS monitoring and alerting

The screenshots in Figure 3.4, Figure 3.5 and Figure 3.6 show the Grafana dashboard of the NEANIAS monitoring system. Grafana visualizes the information stored in InfluxDB and Prometheus.

Figure 3.4 - NEANIAS monitoring Grafana dashboard

D7.5 Operation Activities Report (interim)

Figure 3.5 - NEANIAS monitoring Grafana dashboard

Figure 3.6 - NEANIAS monitoring Grafana dashboard

D7.5 Operation Activities Report (interim)

Figure 3.7 and Figure 3.8 show health and availability information from the Nagios monitoring and alerting system for the DaShaS (Data sharing) and AAI core services.

Figure 3.7 – Nagios: Service Status

Service 'NEANIAS SSO' On Host 'neanias-ss0-nkua'

2021-03-01 00:00:00 to 2021-04-01 00:00:00
Duration: 31d 0h 0m 0s

Service State Breakdowns:

State	Type / Reason	Time	% Total Time	% Known Time
OK	Unscheduled	31d 0h 0m 0s	100.000%	100.000%
	Scheduled	0d 0h 0m 0s	0.000%	0.000%
	Total	31d 0h 0m 0s	100.000%	100.000%
WARNING	Unscheduled	0d 0h 0m 0s	0.000%	0.000%
	Scheduled	0d 0h 0m 0s	0.000%	0.000%
	Total	0d 0h 0m 0s	0.000%	0.000%
UNKNOWN	Unscheduled	0d 0h 0m 0s	0.000%	0.000%
	Scheduled	0d 0h 0m 0s	0.000%	0.000%
	Total	0d 0h 0m 0s	0.000%	0.000%
CRITICAL	Unscheduled	0d 0h 0m 0s	0.000%	0.000%
	Scheduled	0d 0h 0m 0s	0.000%	0.000%
	Total	0d 0h 0m 0s	0.000%	0.000%
Undetermined	Nagios Not Running	0d 0h 0m 0s	0.000%	
	Insufficient Data	0d 0h 0m 0s	0.000%	
	Total	0d 0h 0m 0s	0.000%	
All	Total	31d 0h 0m 0s	100.000%	100.000%

Figure 3.8 – Nagios: Service availability report

D7.5 Operation Activities Report (interim)

3.1.3. NEANIAS Accounting and logging core services

In Figure 3.9 – NEANIAS AAI accountable actions tracked using NEANIAS Accounting Service, a report from the NEANIAS Accounting Service is shown, including accountable actions that the NEANIAS AAI service is tracking with respect to authentication actions for individual services and authenticated users.

Figure 3.9 – NEANIAS AAI accountable actions tracked using NEANIAS Accounting Service

D7.5 Operation Activities Report (interim)

In Figure 3.10 - Log aggregation and statistics using NEANIAS Logging Service, aggregated statistics per service are displayed, showing cumulative numbers of log entries produced as well as high level breakdown based on their severity.

Figure 3.10 - Log aggregation and statistics using NEANIAS Logging Service

D7.5 Operation Activities Report (interim)

In Figure 3.11 - Log filtering using NEANIAS Logging Service, the basic interactive dashboard is presented from which an authorized user can explore, and aggregate logging entries produced by individual services, using the supported underlying domain query language.

Figure 3.11 - Log filtering using NEANIAS Logging Service

D7.5 Operation Activities Report (interim)

3.1.4. Service Management System

In Figure 3.12, the NEANIAS SMS Redmine project is presented with some test users and test tickets in the staging area, while Figure 3.13 presents the documentation of the SMS system as Redmine Wiki pages.

The screenshot shows the Redmine project overview for 'NEANIAS SMS'. The page includes a navigation bar with 'Overview', 'Activity', 'Issues', 'Spent time', 'Gantt', 'Calendar', 'News', 'Documents', 'Wiki', 'Files', and 'Settings'. The 'Overview' section is active, displaying an 'Issue tracking' table and a 'Members' sidebar.

	open	closed	Total
Complaint	1	0	1
Incident	0	0	0
Change request	0	0	0
Improvement request	0	0	0
Access request	2	0	2
Satisfaction survey	0	0	0

Members
 Manager: Attila Farkas, Redmine Admin
 External user: user user
 Service owners: Attila Farkas, Process Owner, Service Owner
 Process owners: Process Owner

Figure 3.12 NEANIAS SMS Redmine project

The screenshot shows the Redmine Wiki page for 'NEANIAS IT service management'. The page contains a hierarchical list of service management topics and a sidebar with Wiki actions.

- Service portfolio management (SPM)
 - SPM Procedures
 - NEANIAS Service Portfolio
- Service level management (SLM)
 - SLM Procedures
 - SLA-OLA Agreements
- Service reporting management (SRM)
 - SRM Procedures
- Customer relationship management (CRM)
 - CRM Procedures
 - NEANIAS user database
- Incident and service request management (ISRM)
 - ISRM Procedures
- Change management (CHM)
 - CHM Procedures
- Release and deployment management (RDM)
 - RDM Procedures
- Continual service improvement management (CSI)
 - CSI Procedures

Templates

- Process template
- Procedure template

→ Files (0)

Updated by Redmine Admin about 2 months ago · 12 revisions
 Also available in: PDF | HTML | TXT

Figure 3.13 NEANIAS SMS documentation as Redmine Wiki

D7.5 Operation Activities Report (interim)

Figure 3.14 presents how the users can submit tickets in the SMS system. The user can select an issue type like Customer Complaint, set the Affected service and the system provides a template for Issue description as well.

Home My page Projects Help Logged in as user1 My account Sign out

NEANIAS SMS Search: NEANIAS SMS

Overview Activity **Issues** Spent time Gantt Calendar News Documents Wiki Files

New issue

Tracker *

Subject *

Status *

Priority *

Affected service *

Issue description *

Files No file chosen (Maximum size: 5 MB)

Figure 3.14 NEANIAS SMS User ticket creation

4. Conclusions

This document, Deliverable D7.5 “Operation Activities Report (interim)” has reported on the operation activities of the NEANIAS project and their operational performance from the point of view of the selected metrics and tools.

In particular, Section 2 has reported on the operation activities regarding service deployment environments, service deployment models and actual service operation and monitoring, while Section 3 has focused on the collection and analysis of service metrics.

As the NEANIAS services enter production, integrate in EOSC and expand their user base, the operation activities become increasingly central, in the perspective of augmenting the overall quality and meet the target performance indicators.

References

- [1] NEANIAS Deliverable D7.1 “Delivery activities methodology and plan”
- [2] NEANIAS Deliverable D7.3 “Software assessment methodology”
- [3] NEANIAS Deliverable D7.4 “Infrastructures integration report (interim)”
- [4] Docker containers: <https://www.docker.com/>
- [5] LXC containers: <https://linuxcontainers.org/>
- [6] NEANIAS Deliverable D8.2 “EOSC service model report”
- [7] NEANIAS Catalogue: <https://catalogue.neanias.eu/home>
- [8] NEANIAS Deliverable D7.2 “Software delivery infrastructure and tools”
- [9] NEANIAS Deliverable D6.1 “Core services architecture, design principles and specifications report – Implementation Plan”
- [10] EGI ARGO EOSC integrated Monitoring – NEANIAS dashboard: <https://neanias.ui.devel.argo.grnet.gr/>

List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
DNS	Domain Name System
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
ISRM	Incident and Service Request Management
FitSM	Family of Standards for lightweight IT Service Management
FQDN	Fully Qualified Domain Name
OIDC	OpenID Connect
NRPE	Nagios Remote Plugin Executor
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure
RDM	Release and Deployment Management
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
SACM	Service Availability and Continuity Management
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SLM	Service Level Management
SMS	Service Management System
SPM	Service Portfolio Management
SLM	Service Level Management
VM	Virtual Machine